

OPTIMIZATION OF AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE IN COMPOSITE MATERIAL

C. Petiau
(Avions Marcel Dassault-Breguet Aviation, Saint-Cloud, France)

1 - INTRODUCTION

Due to their outstanding strength, carbon epoxy materials have gradually invaded aircraft structures as manufacturing and design methods were being perfected. For Dassault aircraft this evolution, since the early seventies, is presented on plate 1. It is worth pointing out, that to-day composite materials represent the best part of Rafale structure.

Fortunately the technology of composite materials has just been preceded by the development of Finite Element methods, which has allowed to resolve rather easily the problem of stress calculation with anisotropic materials.

The two main remaining problems were :

- the elaboration of adequate failure criteria ; this problem is far from being perfectly solved to-day and we will come back to it in § 5,
- the organization of drawing and analysis loop to obtain the lightest solution which will be our main purpose in this discussion.

Classical design of structure was achieved with the "fully stress design" process (F.S.D.), made of iterations of drawing and analyses with reinforcements where the structure is not sufficiently strong and lightening when there are strength margins.

Yet with metallic structure, we had demonstrated (see reference 1) that this approach was neither optimum nor efficient, particularly when design constraints due to flexibility are involved as eigen frequency, aerodistorsion, flutter. With composite materials, even when only constraints of strength of materials exist, the designer is unable to intuitate the lightest ply disposal supporting stress flows of several cases of load. The problem being inextricable for a human brain alone when aeroelastic constraints are involved.

These reasons led Dassault to develop an organization for composite design, the keystone of which consists in mathematical optimization technics.

This organization is entirely supported by the CATIA-ELFINI software which integrates in a common system : C.A.D, mesh generation, F.E. analysis, load and aeroelasticity, optimization and visualisation of all inputs and outputs.

The system works, on request, either in an interactive or in a batch mode, and uses a common data base automatically managed. It is particularly well suited for composite materials study :

- in C.A.D. with tools for direct layers manipulation,
- in mesh generation with direct recognition of composite material and automatic acquisition of characteristics in C.A.D. model,
- in F.E. analysis, with the adaptation of the classical library of elements to composite situation, and a special library for "edge effect" and a lot of processors for special part analyses (see § 5),

- in optimization, with design variables as the number of plies in each direction, constraints of composite failure criteria and special manufacturing rules,
- in visualization, with a lot of specially adapted pictures for composite inputs and outputs (number of plies in each direction, ply by ply stress and failure criteria, envelope failure criteria).

We are going to present a more detailed view of :

- the optimization technics for composite materials which is mainly used to set the general dimensioning of the structure. It is supported by F.E. models of the whole aircraft which are elaborated only from the rough definition of external shape and internal architecture, the result of this optimization being the starting point of detail drawing,
- the special tools for the detail checking analysis of composite structure,
- the organization for drawing and analysis which results from necessities of composite design and present possibilities of computer tools.

2 - THE OPTIMIZATION METHOD

We have described it in several papers (Ref. 1 and 2) ; now we present the operational tool as it was used for "Rafale" design ; the organization is iterative with the flow-chart below.

- Cost function

The current goal in optimization is weight minimization. Nevertheless, in some cases, weight can be taken as a constraint, the objective being maximization of safety margin.

- Design variables

The characterization of the optimization design variables is made on groups of Finite Elements (plate 3). The choice of these variables partly takes into account manufacturing constraints and tooling rules for metallic material.

For a composite material, the design variables are the number of plies in each direction for each group.

The number of design variables often reaches 500, which can act simultaneously over several analysis models.

- Constraints

They come from the different analysis branches of ELFINI, we can consider simultaneously :

- . Various failure criteria (especially for composite materials), computed from static stresses for all the main cases of loads
- . Local buckling criteria
- . Limited displacements
- . Aeroelastic variation of aerodynamic derivatives
- . Dynamic natural frequencies
- . Flutter speed and aeroelastic dynamic damping
- . Various technological constraints (as minimum values of design variables, and limitations of the thickness variation between adjacent design variables).

The constraints considered during the same optimization can come from several analysis models (ex : symmetric and anti-symmetric F.E. aircraft model, local buckling analysis by Rayleigh-Ritz method, local refined F.E. analysis , different external loads configurations for dynamic and flutter, variation of shape due to control surface deflections, etc.).

It can easily be demonstrated, (see table 1 and references 1 and 2) that the computation of derivatives of static stresses, displacements, and aeroelastic coefficients is equivalent to solutions with "dummy" case of loads.

We often take into account up to 5000 constraints simultaneously.

- Mathematical optimization

Starting from the analysis and derivation of constraints, we use an explicit non linear approximation of the constraints in terms of the design variables, mainly the formulation of inverse variables ; by a change of variables, it leads to minimize an homographic function (weight) subject to linear constraints ; this problem is easily solved by projected conjugate gradient algorithm ; the cost of the mathematical optimization step is low.

The mathematical optimization step gives a prediction of the optimum, from which we start new iterations.

<p><u>FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS</u></p> <p>Displacement computation :</p> $X = [K]^{-1} F$ <p>Strength, stress computation :</p> $\sigma = \left[\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial X} \right] X$ <p><u>OPTIMIZATION CONSTRAINT DERIVATION</u></p> <p>Displacement derivation :</p> $\Delta X = - [K]^{-1} [[\Delta K] X - \Delta F]$ <p>Strength, stress derivation :</p> $\Delta \sigma = - \left[\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial X} \right] [K]^{-1} [[\Delta K] X - \Delta F] \quad (1)$ $\Delta \sigma = - [[K]^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial X} \right]]' [[\Delta K] X - \Delta F] \quad (2)$ <p>(1) number of resolutions equal number of load cases (2) number of resolutions equal number of constraint operators</p>

Table 1

The number of iterations, needed to get the global convergence, ranges from 3 to 5.

The cost of all the iterations of optimization ranges about 8 to 15 times the cost of the analysis.

- Final touches

Generally the theoretical optimum obtained from the optimization algorithm needs some modifications, since it does not often represent a realistic design. Starting from the table of the constraints derivatives, the final touches consist in examining interactively the effect of small modifications, directly given by the designer during the drawing. The program shows instantaneously the picture of new safety margin and violated constraints (see plate 6).

3 - SPECIAL FEATURES OF OPTIMIZATION WITH COMPOSITE MATERIAL

The organization described above is well suited for a composite material with the addition of following specificities.

- Failure criteria analysis and derivation

Inside the optimization loop we use failure criteria of the "Tsaï-Hill" family as :

$$C = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_x^2}{\sigma_{xad}^2} + S_1 * \frac{\sigma_y^2}{\sigma_{yad}^2} + S_2 * \frac{\tau_{xy}^2}{\tau_{xyad}^2} - S_3 * \frac{\sigma_x \sigma_y}{\sigma_{xad} \sigma_{yad}} \right)}$$

with

σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} : stress tensor components

σ_{xad} , σ_{yad} , τ_{xyad} and $S_i = 0$ or 1 : criteria parameters

Arguments of criteria are adapted to each situation (eg : tension, compression, bending, holed panel, etc...), this by calibration on more sophisticated criteria (see § 5) and on test results.

Due to the fact that, at a given point, the final failure mode is not known beforehand, it is necessary to handle constraints on all potential failure modes simultaneously.

This is achieved at a relatively low cost if the derivation is performed in two steps :

- compute strain tensor and its derivative by formula 1 of table 1 (3 components common to all plies with membrane assumption),
- starting from strain tensor and material Hook law, calculate ply by ply failure criteria and their derivative.

- Local buckling criteria

Even if optimization can handle directly global buckling, for management and cost effectiveness it is generally preferable to calculate and to derivate buckling criteria with the following post-processing analysis :

- On the general finite element model, calculation and derivation of stress flows of structural meshes,
- Local buckling load factors and their derivatives calculation by a Rayleigh Ritz method (see table 2).

Sizes of meshes for local buckling analyses are independent from their representation in the global F.E. model, and they can be tuned to be suited to the actual stiffening.

In the optimization loop, stacking sequences are not taken into account (assumption of material homogeneity through panel thickness), for the sake of algorithm simplicity, and due to difficulties to express lays covering and stacking constraints in drawing.

The order of buckling modes can change between iterations ; this can cause a non convergence of iterations if all potential buckling modes are not controlled simultaneously (see reference 2).

- Design constraints

These constraints express the fact that results of optimization must correspond to a real drawing of composite panel, which must be made of stacked layers with special rules for easy manufacturing.

Design constraints are handled at two levels :

- . Inside the optimization loop, as by placing constraints checking a minimum number or a given minimum proportion of plies in each direction, or a maximum slope of thickness (constraints corresponding to linear inequalities on design variable),
- . After mathematical convergence, by automatic thicknesses rounding off to get a whole number of plies, and by a special half interactive program which transforms the stacking of ply by area, which are the rough output of optimization, into a proper cut out of layers.

<u>LOCAL BUCKLING ANALYSIS</u>	
<u>BY RAYLEIGH-RITZ METHOD</u>	
<u>RAYLEIGH-RITZ MODEL</u>	
External load fluxes :	$\Phi = \begin{matrix} \Phi_{x0} \\ \Phi_{y0} \\ \Phi_{xy0} \end{matrix} = \rho \Phi_0$
Normal deflection :	
$w = \sum a_{mn} x^m y^n L(x,y)$	$V = \begin{matrix} a_{11} \\ \dots \\ a_{mn} \end{matrix}$
<u>BUCKLING FACTORS</u>	
Buckling initiation :	$W_1 = W_2$
$W_1 =$ Bending elastic energy	
$W_2 =$ Membrane work of external loads ($W_2 = \rho U_2$)	
	$W_1 = \rho U_2$
$\min \rho = W_1 / U_2 \iff \delta W_1 / \delta V - \rho \delta U_2 / \delta V = 0$	
	$[K - \rho G] V = 0$
<u>DERIVATION OF BUCKLING FACTORS</u>	
$\rho = \frac{V^t K(\lambda) V}{V^t G(\phi) V}$	
$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{V^t \partial K / \partial \lambda \cdot V}{V^t G(\phi) \cdot V} + \rho \frac{V^t \partial G / \partial \phi \cdot \partial \phi / \partial \lambda \cdot V}{V^t G(\phi) \cdot V}$	

Table 2

4 - EXAMPLE OF APPLICATION OF OPTIMIZATION OF CARBON EPOXY STRUCTURE

We present two significative examples of optimization calculation of carbon epoxy parts for a combat aircraft.

- Optimization of a combat aircraft wing

We resume here the configuration of the optimization of a carbon epoxy Delta Wing box, corresponding to the mesh presented on plate 2, with the design variable patch of plate 3.

We had used two analysis models for static and aeroelasticity with the survey of flutter on three external load configurations.

	MODEL 1	MODEL 2
F.E. models	wing model with a representation of other part of the aircraft by super element technique (3544 DOF) symmetric and antisymmetric analysis	complete plane 13003 DOF symmetric and antisymmetric analysis
Design Variable	476 Design Variable (Number of plies in 4 directions)	
Static cases of loads	24 cases of loads combined from symmetric and antisymmetric	0
Failure criteria	476 failure criteria equivalent "Tsaï-Hill criteria"	
Buckling criteria	144 critical buckling factor issued from 77 local buckling analyses of composite plates by Rayleigh Ritz method	0
Static aeroelastic constraint	0	7 control surface efficiencies and minimal roll speed
Flutter		5 flutter speeds and 60 aeroelastic dampings corresponding to 3 external load configuration
Technological constraint	374 constraints on composite lay-up (thickness shape, maximum and minimum ratio between each ply direction)	

On plate 4, we present the history of convergence in weight. Drawing constraints and flutter constraints have been successively introduced later in order to see their influence. The optimum values of design variables are presented plate 3, and the corresponding cut out of plies is presented plate 5 (obtained automatically).

- Optimum design of a vertical fin

The lay out of the box and the rudder in carbon epoxy are optimized considering static cases of load for two rudder deflection cases, and constraints on rudder aeroelastic efficiencies and dynamic frequencies, see plate 6.

The exact configuration of this optimization follows :

	MODEL 1	MODEL 2
F.E. models	Fin model (1800 DOF) with a super element of the whole aircraft (plate 6)	Fin model with a deflected rudder (plate 6)
Design Variables	237 Design Variable on the number of lay, spars and ribs flanges (area) and web (thickness)	
Static Load cases	3	1
Failure criteria	190 failure criteria on composite materials with holes	190
Buckling criteria	98 buckling criteria computed from Rayleigh Ritz models for panel buckling analysis	82
Displacements	1 on the step between box and rudder	0
Aeroelasticity	8 constraints on fin and rudder yaw efficiencies for two Mach number	0
Dynamic	Frequencies of 1st flexion mode and rudder mode	0
Technology	107 constraints on plies repartitions and on minimum distance between lay interruptions	

5 - CHECKING ANALYSIS

It must be understood that, if optimization tool is indispensable to reach rationally a good general drawing, the result must be justified in detail with more complex analyses than those which can be handle inside the optimization loop. Here we present some of the most typical detail checking analyses.

- "Point stress analysis" for holed composite panel

This empirical criterion has been developed to take into account the microscopic effects of accomodation and delamination in the area of stress concentration of a hole, which attenuates the stress concentration factor in the case of short diameter hole.

The criterion takes into account stresses at a given distance of the edge of the hole.

After being calibrated on test results, point stress criteria give proper results for multi-axial stresses, and effects of hole diameter, hole inhabitation, and bearing.

The problem was to make the handling of point stress criteria as easy for users as classical Tsai-Hill family criteria.

In this purpose, we have developed a special F.E. procedure which elaborates automatically a F.E. mesh around the hole (see plate 7) and performs the non linear F.E. analysis (bearing contact non linearity). With a proper organization of programming the computer cost remains trifle. This feature allows to establish complete strength abacus with the influence of three components of stress tensor can be elaborated (see plate 8).

- "Bolt by bolt" analysis

This type of checking analysis is required in the area of load transfer by fastening (see plates 9 and 10 : presentation of the analysis of carbon epoxy wing of V10F).

Fastened panels are represented by an accurate mesh of plate elements (at least two elements between each bolt), and bolts or rivets are represented by "beam bolt" elements (beam elements with a special penalty keeping parallel the two tips).

The bearing stiffness of a "beam bolt" is calibrated with test results and on 3D non linear analyses.

Point stress analysis is to be used as post processing of "bolt by bolt" analysis : a 2D finite element mesh is automatically generated around the bolt and mixed boundary conditions are extracted from the global mesh (bolt bearing load and displacement on 2D mesh outline, see plate 10).

With the CATIA-ELFINI system these operations are automatic (the user has only to point out the considered bolt).

- Post-buckling analysis

The strength of thin panels, which buckle before ultimate load, must be analyzed precisely in order to make the composite design competitive with the metallic design, by respect of weight considerations.

For this reason, we have developed in CATIA-ELFINI an original algorithm called "preconditioned BFGS with an exact Line Search". This algorithm is strongly adapted to take into account the biquadratic character of total potential in geometrically non linear problems. It can handle the most severe snap through conditions (see references 3 and 4).

On plate 11 we present an example of this type of calculation concerning test of fuselage panel in carbon epoxy.

The strategy is to take constraints of linear buckling inside optimization loop. This buckling load level is lower than ultimate load, and must be validated later by post buckling analysis.

- Edge effect, delamination

In the past, edge effects have been dealt with in an abundant literature ; it is very simply treated with special 2D finite element with 3D strain and stress fields (see reference 5).

If the contemplation of the singular stress field at edges of interlayers is not very helpful, it is more effective to associate delamination propagation calculation with "edge effect type" analysis. We compute the rate of energy release of unbuttoning of layers, it gives directly G coefficients of fracture mechanics (see plate 12).

These delamination tolerance analyses are needed for :

- . edge delamination propagation (rather uncommon with practical stacking)
- . tearing-off analysis of bonded or cocured stiffeners (see plate 13)
- . core delamination propagation evaluation, where it must be associated with post-buckling analysis (see plate 13).

6 - ORGANIZATION OF DESIGN PROCESS

Now we have the following organization for design of composite structures, from the preliminary project to the delivery of manufacturing drawings :

- . Start from a CATIA drawing of only external shape and a brief definition of internal architecture
- . Elaborate, by CATIA-MESH, a first simple general F.E. mesh of the whole aircraft (10-30000 D.O.F.) with approximate cross sections and thicknesses (see plate 2). The model is adjusted with simple cases of load
- . Static aeroelasticity and loads, which give the envelope cases of loads and show the latent problems of aeroelasticity
- . Examination of internal load fields and stresses for selection of "strength of material" constraints in optimization
- . Dynamic modes computation with the various external store configurations, flutter problem recognition
- . First run of optimization
- . Drawings of the structure supported by :
 - interactive test of authoritative modifications of results of optimization to make drawing easier, this with the final touches module,
 - changes and additions of constraints,
 - critical examination of "cost of requirements", directly obtained from "Lagrange multipliers" of optimization, which with composite materials allows to appreciate the real influence of safety margin on uncertain criteria,
 - details checking analyses supported by methods described above in § 5. They are performed taking proper boundary conditions in the Finite Element model of the whole aircraft via a super Element technics. Detail checking analyses must validate the simplified criteria used for mathematical optimization ; otherwise optimization must be replayed with calibrated criteria.

Although a single run of mathematical optimization lasts only one night, the optimization job actually can remain inside the computer more than six months, in order to examine detail analysis effects, the influence of the choice of constraints and alternative designs.

7 - CONCLUSION

The tendency would be to include more and more detailed analyses inside the mathematical optimization loop. This evolution is hindered by the difficulties of the task.

The tool described above represents the achievement of the first level of structural optimization, where geometry is given and mass and stiffness matrices are linear functions of design variables.

Significant progress is not easy. It corresponds to including inside optimization :

- "bending" design variables
- post-buckling analysis and rules of effective width
- stacking order of plies and constraints on layers cut out
- shape optimization, which is also implicitly necessary in the above functionalities.

Independently from their theoretical difficulty these developments need a higher level of integration of F.E. optimization with C.A.D. ; in particular the architecture of C.A.D. system must support the description of design variable and of drawing constraints.

Another promising field of research is to use technics of artificial intelligence to pilot the design, it seems to be one mean to manage optimization with discontinuous evolution of design variables. Presently we have started the development of this technics at the level of check sizing of carbon fiber panels. It rests on a knowledge basis composed of rules, referring technological constraints and methods of calculations.

REFERENCES

- 1 - C. PETIAU & G. LECINA
Elements finis et optimisation des structures aéronautiques
Agard conference proceeding N° 280
"the use of computer as a design tool" - Munich 1978.
- 2 - G. LECINA & C. PETIAU
Optimization of aircraft structure
Foundations of structure optimization approach
Edited by A.J. Morris - 1982 John Waley & Sons Ltd.
- 3 - C. PETIAU & C. CORNUAULT
Efficient algorithms for post-buckling computation
6th international symposium on computing methods in applied science and engineering - Versailles 1983.
- 4 - C. PETIAU & C. CORNUAULT
Algorithmes efficaces pour le calcul des équilibres en post-flambement
3ème colloque : tendances actuelles en calcul des structures
Edited by J.P. Grellier et J.M. Campel - Editions Pluralis Paris.
- 5 - PIPES, R. BYRON & N.J. PAGANO
Interlaminar stresses in composite laminates under uniform axial extension -
J. Composite Materials - october 1970, pp. 538-548.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL IN DASSAULT AIRCRAFT FROM "MIRAGE III" TO "RAFALE" AND "HERMES"

PLATE 1

GENERAL MESH OF COMBAT AIRCRAFT

PLATE 2

OPTIMIZATION OF CARBON EPOXY WING

UPPER PANEL OPTIMUM LAY UP

LOWER PANEL OPTIMUM LAY UP

OPTIMIZATION OF CARBON EPOXY WING HISTORY OF CONVERGENCE

PLATE 4

INTERACTIVE LAY UP DESIGN USING OPTIMUM PATTERN

PLATE 5

OPTIMIZATION OF CARBON EPOXY FIN

MODEL 1
NO RUDDER DEFLECTION

MODEL 2
WITH RUDDER DEFLECTION

OPTIMAL LAY UP

ACTIVE CONSTRAINTS AT OPTIMUM

MESH OF A POINT STRESS ANALYSIS
(AUTOMATICALLY GENERATED BY ELFINI)

PLATE 7

"STRENGTH ABACUS"
BY POINT STRESS ANALYSIS

"BOLT BY BOLT" ANALYSIS
ON THE V10F CARBON EPOXY WING

-50-

"AUTOMATIC POINT STRESS" ANALYSIS
AFTER "BOLT BY BOLT" ANALYSIS

POST-BUCKLING ANALYSIS OF A CURVED CARBON EPOXY PANEL
(TEST ON FUSELAGE PANEL OF COMBAT AIRCRAFT)

PLATE 11

EDGE DELAMINATION ANALYSIS

PLATE 12

TEARING OF A STIFFENER

PROPAGATION OF DELAMINATION IN COMPRESSION
BY POST-BUCKLING ANALYSIS